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RADIO FREQUENCY IDENTIFICATION BASED LIBRARY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Radio frequency identification (RFID) is a rapidly emerging technology which allows productivity and convenience. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) is a new generation of Auto Identification and Data collection technology which helps to automate business processes and allows identification of large number of tagged objects like books, using radio waves. This paper proposes RFID Based Library Management System that would allow fast Transaction flow and will make it easy to handle the issue and return of books from the library without much intervention of manual book keeping which benefits by adding properties of traceability and security. The proposed system is based on RFID readers and passive RFID tags that are able to electronically store information that can be read with the help of the RFID reader. This system would be able to issue and return books via RFID tags and also calculates the corresponding fine associated with the time period of the absence of the book from the library database.

KEYWORDS — radio frequency identification (RFID), RFID tags, RFID reader, microcontroller, GSM.